

PROBLEMS ABOUT CORONAVIRUS PATHOGENESIS AND MEDICATIONS ACTUALLY USED

Coronavirus Covid-19 uses ACE2 (*angiotensin-converting enzyme II*), that is an essential regulator of heart function expressed in the heart, lung, kidney and gastrointestinal tract, but also acts a functional receptor for the spike glycoprotein (S) – it's the largest structure and makes the distinct spikes on the surface of the virus - of coronavirus to enters in the host's cells, because it's has an high affinity binding with Covid-19.

ACE2 structure

- The expression of ACE2 in adipose tissue (including subcutaneous and visceral) is significantly higher than that in lung, so Obesity was reported to increase vulnerability to infection.
- In five types of cancer is also significantly higher the ACE2 expression that in the lung: CESC (*Cervical squamous cell carcinoma and endocervical adenocarcinoma*), PAAD (*Pancreatic adenocarcinoma*), READ (*Rectum adenocarcinoma*), KIRP (*Kidney renal papillary cell carcinoma*) and KIRC (*Kidney renal clear cell carcinoma*).¹

- There are many other conditions -like *diabetes*- that generate high expression of ACE2 activity, like genetic predisposition, 'cause ACE2 is on the X chromosome (Xp22). To be a smoker, exposed to high smog levels, to be a man or elder.

Once the virus enters in host, it causes a downregulation of its binder ACE2, causing severe disorders in many districts where ACE2 could acts, especially cardiovascular diseases, kidney failure and cerebral/cognitive impairments.

Actually is used INTERFERON to lower ACE2 expression activity, but the problem is that this type of medication causes an energetic immune response, which added to the organic immune reaction, can result in a "*cytokine storm*", a severe inflammatory state, with all the consequences of case: in extremis heart failure, development of neurotoxins, respiratory diseases and unexpected death. In addition, some other medications can cause hyper reactive immune system.

One factor that makes conditions of patient infected by Covid-19 worse, it's exactly "CYTOKINE STORM".²

Children have a simple immune system, so complications are rare.

In addition, Covid-19 dramatically lower number and exhausts function of T cells: CD4+ and CD8+; these contribute to the modulation of cytokine, reducing probability of an excessive immune reaction, so prevent the worsening of general and respiratory conditions, besides have a memory that can prevents a reinfection.

WHAT CATEGORIES ARE MOST AT RISK?

Men, elders, smokers, exposed to the smog, obese, diabetics, affected by some type of cancer (sudden written), because have higher ACE2 expression activity AND who had an hyper reactive immune system → cytokine storm → severe inflammatory condition.

WHY CHILDREN HAVE LESS SEVERE SYMPTOMS OR NONE?

Children have a **STRAIGHTFORWARD** immune system, while **ELDER** often have a compromised system, with **DEFICIENCY OF T CELLS**, that modulate immune reaction.

IT'S POSSIBLE TO GET REINFECTED?

Yes.

The **ANTIBODIES** are formed and **persist** for a **MEDIUM-SHORT TIME**. The problem is that **Covid-19 REDUCES** and affects **FUNCTION** of T cells **CD4+** and **CD8+**, so the **memory for the virus**.³ A **secondary infection** is more severe, because our **immune system + medications** like some hormones and **interferons** used to treat primary infection can cause an **excessive inflammatory state**.

References:

¹ Jia, X.; Yin, C.; Lu, Sen, Y. ; Ch; Liu, Q.; Bai, J.; Lu, Y. Two Things about COVID-19 Might Need Attention. Preprints 2020, 2020020315 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202002.0315.v1)

² Bo Diao, Chenhui Wang, Yingjun Tan, Xiewan Chen, Ying Liu, Lifeng Ning, Li Chen, Min Li, Yueping Liu, Gang Wang, Zilin Yuan, Zeqing Feng, Yuzhang Wu, Yongwen Chen doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.02.18.20024364>

³ Cecere, Thomas & Todd, Stephanie & Leroith, Tanya. (2012). Regulatory T Cells in Arterivirus and Coronavirus Infections: Do They Protect Against Disease or Enhance it?. Viruses. 4. 833-46. 10.3390/v4050833